

A REVISION OF THE GENUS *VACHONUS* TIKADER AND BASTAWADE (ARACHNIDA: SCORPIONIDA: BUTHIDAE) WITH TWO NEW SPECIES FROM PAKISTAN WITH REFERENCE TO THEIR CHROMATOGRAPHY AND ELECTROPHORASIS OF VENOM

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ABSTRACT

Two new species of the genus *Vachonus* Tikader and Bastawade are described from Sindh, Chachro and Kotri, Pakistan with special reference to their male genitalia, Gel chromatography and Electrophoresis of the venom. These species are compared with closest allies. A key to the species is also formulated for easy identification and relationship of the included taxa are also briefly discussed using apomorphic characters.

Key Words: New species, *Vachonus*, Scorpionidae, Chromatography, Electrophoresis, venom, Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Tikader and Bastawade (1983) described a new genus *Vachonus* to accommodate a new species *rajasthanicus* from Rajasthan and *atrostriotus* Pocock (1897 and 1900) under the genus *Buthus*. The present authors collected a series of specimens from Chachro and Kotri, Sindh, Pakistan identified as new species of the genus *Vachonus* by their apomorphic characters.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The animals were collected from the Chachro, Kotri, Sindh, Pakistan and were killed with the help of 10% formalin and preserved in 70% Alcohol. For the study of Male genitalia the specimens were dissected out by removing the tergites of mesosoma. After dissection the aedeagus was mounted on slide then taken the photograph using microscope and photographic camera. For the study of electrophoresis and chromatography the technique generally followed by Amir *et. al.* 1994, a, b, c, d and 1995, 2003, 2004 and 2008.

RESULTS GENUS: *VACHONUS*

Vachonus Tikader and Bastawade, 1983, *Faun. Ind. Arachn.* 3: 173-185.

Buthus Pocock, 1897. *J. Bombay nat. Hist. Soc.*, 11: 105; 1900, *Faun. Brit. Ind. Arachn.*, 20.

Diagnostic feature

Mesosomal tergites tricarinated but carinae not spiniform posteriorly. Metasomal segment II with very weak or rudimentary lateral carinae. Inferior lateral carinae of segment 5th unevenly granular and lobate on posterior portion. Vesicle granular on ventral surface and provided with a sub-aculeus nodule. Cheliceral fixed finger provided with two minute teeth on ventral surface. Tarsus (movable finger) of the pedipalp with 2-4 distal granules just proximal to apical tooth and lateral granules some times smaller than median and inner granules. Tarosomere II with spines. Cephalo-thoracic sternum triangular. Trichobothria dorsal 1, dorsal 3 and dorsal 4 on femur form β angle, trichobothria est distal to db on immovable finger.

Comparative note

This genus is most closely related to *Compsobuthus* Vachon (1950) in having posterior median carinae distinct, strongly spiniform posteriorly and anteriorly joining with central median carinae, mesosomal tergites tricarinated and the carinae strongly spiniform posteriorly, but it can easily be separated from the same in having posterior median carinae of carapace joining the central median carinae but neither straight nor spiniform posteriorly, mesosomal tergites tricarinated but carinae not spiniform posteriorly and by the other characters as noted in the description.

Type species

Vachonus rajasthanicus Vachon.

Distribution

India and Pakistan.

**Key to the species of the genus *Vachonus*
Tikader and Bastawade**

1. Movable finger of pedipalp provided with 10-11 very minute (exterior) granules, pectinal teeth 22 in number in female and 28 in male; aculeus longer than vesicular length2
- Movable finger of pedipalp provided with 12-lateral teeth of equal size to median teeth, pectinal teeth 26 in number in female and 20 in male, aculeus as long as vesicular length.....3
2. Entire surface weakly granular, pectinal teeth 22, Tarsomere II flat, row of mid ventral spicules present.....*rajasthanicus* Vachon
- Entire surface very weakly granular, pectinal teeth 31, Tarsomere II cylindrical, row of mid ventral spicules absent.....*V. asiyae* sp.n.
3. Entire surface not evenly granular, pectinal teeth 26, pedipalp with more bulbous hand.....*V. atrostriatus* Pocock.....
- Entire surface weakly granular, pectinal teeth 29, pedipalp with globular hand.....*V. iqbalii* sp.n.

***Vachonus asiyae* sp. n.
(Figs. 1-11)****Colouration**

Body generally mustard colour.

Prosoma

Entire surface of carapace very weakly granular, all carinae very weakly granular, ocular tubercles dark black and granular, anterior margins granular and provided with 30-32 small blackish setae, lateral margins smooth but more smooth on anterior portion.

Pedipalp

Manus globular, elongated, longer than femur, shorter than carapace, almost all carinae strong and granular, outer and anterior side provided with a crenulated crest of 20-21 denticular tubercles, patella longer than femur but always shorter than carapace, carinae on outer side smooth, on dorsal and ventral sides weakly granular, inner or anterior surface provided almost crenulated crest with 15-sub-denticular tubercles, manus or hand elongated and length of underhand shorter than femur, but movable finger longer than carapace, dentition on the fingers consisting of three rows of non-imbricated teeth granular on the fixed and movable finger, trichobothrial pattern of pedipalp 'A' type.

Legs

Femur weakly granular and patella smooth and carinae crenulated, tibia with one tibial spur on the legs III and IV, size 0.1 cm., pedal spurs spiny, tarsomere I laterally flat and not provided with setae on dorsal and ventral margins, tarsomere II cylindrical, row of mid ventral spinules absent.

Pectin

Pectin well developed and almost two times longer than wide, ten middle lamellae present, fulcra nearly triangular, pectin yellow with 31 teeth.

Genital operculum

Genital operculum wider than long, and sclerites slightly divided on posterior portion from which small genital papillae produced in male, sternum small and triangular.

Mesosoma

All tergites weakly granular, on posterior portion, tergite VII provided with one pair of lateral weakly granule, sternites I-IV weakly granular and each provided with slit-like stigmata for lungs.

Metasoma

Cauda four times as short as carapace, first segment shorter than wide, segments I-IV with dorsal carinae weakly crenulated, dentition on posterior portion much more elevated on segment III and IV, dorso-lateral carinae evenly crenulated, lateral carinae weakly developed only on posterior portion of segment III-IV.

Telson

Telson with vesicle not deep as segment V, ventral surface densely granular, ventral median crest not developed, sub-aculeus nodule weakly present, aculeus not curved, as long as vesicle.

Flagellum 0.5 mm long, elongated and whip-like, trunk 0.4 mm long and 0.15 mm wide, trunk region with semi-diameter, pedicel very flat, 0.3 mm long and 0.15 mm wide, sperm spine hook-like, sperm tube narrowed and elongated.

Material examined

Holotype, Male, Pakistan Sindh, Chachro, 7-9-93, leg. Asiya, lodged a MEMUK, No.126.

Paratypes: 7 females, other data same as holotype, lodged at ZMUK.

Comparative note

This new species is most closely related to *Vachonus rajasthanicus* Vachon in having entire

surface granular, 22 pectinal teeth are present but it can easily be separated from the same in having entire surface very weakly granular, 31 pectinal teeth are present and by the other characters as noted in the key and description.

***Vachonus iqbali* Sp. n.**
(Figs. 12-22)

Colouration

Body generally yellow mustard colour.

Prosoma

Carapace: Entire surface of carapace weakly granular, all carinae smooth, ocular tubercles black and blackish brown, anterior margins weakly granular and provided with 26-27 small blackish setae, lateral margins weakly crenulated on anterior portion.

TABLE 1
Measurement in cm/mm meristic characters of the male holotype *Vachonus asiyaae* Sp. n.

Characters	Holotype Male
Total length	4.0 cm.
Carapace length	0.6 cm.
Mesosoma length	0.7 cm.
Metasoma length	2.7 cm.
I segment length/width	0.48/0.20 cm.
II segment length/width	0.50/0.23 cm.
III segment length/width	0.55/0.25 cm.
IV segment length/width	0.58/0.28 cm.
V segment length/width	0.6/0.3 cm.
Telson length	0.6 cm.
Vesicle length/width	0.4/0.25 cm.
Aculeus length	0.2 cm.
Pedipalp length	1.75 cm.
Femur length/width	0.4/0.2 cm.
Patella length/width	0.5/0.25 cm.
Chela length/width	0.85/0.25 cm.
Fixed finger length	4.5 cm.
Movable finger length	4.7 cm.
Chelicera, Chela length/width	0.2/0.1 cm.
Fixed finger length	0.1 cm.
Movable finger length	0.11 cm.
Pectinal tooth count	31.
Male Genitalia	1.2 mm.

TABLE 2
Variation in tarsomere II spine counts in *Vachonus asiyaae* sp. n. on each specimen, the spine of the left and right legs of each pair were counted.

Legs	Margin	4	5	6	7	8
I	Prolateral	4	3	4	7	5
	Retrolateral	3	3	3	5	4
II	Prolateral	5	4	5	7	3
	Retrolateral	5	5	5	5	5
III	Prolateral	8	5	7	8	9
	Retrolateral	5	4	7	8	7
IV	Prolateral	7	6	4	6	7
	Retrolateral	7	6	5	5	4

TABLE 3
Measurement in cm/mm meristic characters of the male holotype *Vachonus iqbali* sp.n.

Characters	Holotype Male
Total length	5.25 cm.
Carapace length	0.7 cm.
Mesosoma length	1.8 cm.
Metasoma length	2.75 cm.
I segment length/width	0.5/0.3 cm.
II segment length/width	0.52/0.32 cm.
III segment length/width	0.55/0.35 cm.
IV segment length/width	0.58/0.38 cm.
V segment length/width	0.6/0.4 cm.
Telson length	0.65 cm.
Vesicle length/width	0.3/0.3 cm.
Aculeus length	0.35 cm.
Pedipalp length	1.9 cm.
Femur length/width	0.4/0.2 cm.
Patella length/width	0.5/0.25 cm.
Chela length/width	1.0/0.3 cm.
Fixed finger length	0.5 cm.
Movable finger length	0.57 cm.
Chelicera, Chela length/width	0.4/0.2 cm.
Fixed finger length	0.15 cm.
Movable finger length	0.16 cm.
Pectinal tooth count	29
Male Genitalia	1.5 cm.

TABLE 4
Variation in tarsomere II spine counts in
***Vachonus iqbalii* Sp. n. on each specimen,**
the spine of the left and right legs of
each pair were counted.

Legs	Margin	4	5	6	7	8
I	Prolateral	7	5	4	6	8
	Retrolateral	5	4	4	7	8
II	Prolateral	7	7	6	5	5
	Retrolateral	6	7	6	4	6
III	Prolateral	8	5	7	8	4
	Retrolateral	8	5	7	7	4
IV	Prolateral	7	4	5	4	5
	Retrolateral	8	4	5	4	5

Pedipalp

Manus globular longer than femur, shorter than carapace, almost all carinae granular, outer and anterior side provided with a crenulated crest, 15 -17 denticular tubercles, patella longer than femur but always shorter than carapace, inner or anterior surface provided almost granular crest with 18 sub-denticular tubercles, manus or hand globular and length of underhand longer than femur, fixed finger almost as long as femur but movable finger shorter than carapace, dentition on the fixed and movable finger, trichobothrial pattern of pedipalp 'A' type.

Legs

Femur weakly granular, patella smooth and carinae crenulated, tibia with one strong tibial spur, on the legs III and IV, size 0.1 cm., pedal spurs spiny, tarsomere II cylindrical, mid-ventral spinules are absent.

Pectin

Pectin well developed and almost two and one fourth times longer than wide, six middle lamellae present, fulcra nearly triangular, lamellae and fulcra clothed with microscopic bristles, pectin yellow with 29-teeth.

Genital operculum

Genital operculum almost as long as wide and sclerites slightly divided on posterior portion from which small genital papillae produced in male, sternum small and triangular.

Mesosoma

All tergites weakly granular but more granular on posterior portion of each tergite, sternites I-IV weakly

granular and each provided with slit-like stigmata for book lungs.

Metasoma:

Cauda four times longer than carapace, first segment shorter than wide, segments I-IV with dorsal carinae crenulated, dentiform on posterior portion much more elevated on segment III and IV, dorso-lateral carinae evenly crenulated, lateral carinae weakly developed only on posterior portion of segment III-IV.

Telson

Telson with vesicle less wider or deeper than segment V, ventral surface densely smooth, ventral median crest not developed, sub-aculeus nodule absent, aculeus not curved, as long as vesicle.

Male genitalia

Flagellum 0.65 mm long, membranous and elastic, trunk 0.6 mm long and 0.1 mm wide, trunk cylindrical basally dilated, pedicel 0.3 mm long, 0.1 mm wide, pedicel very flat, sperm spine small hook-like, sperm tube narrowed elongated.

Material examined

Holotype, Male, Pakistan: Kotri (Sindh), 4-12-1985, leg. Alt, lodged at MEMUK No.155.

Paratypes, 6 females, other data same as holotype, lodged at ZMUK.

Comparative note

This new species is most closely related to *Vachonus atrostriatus* Pocock, in having movable finger of pedipalp provided with 12-lateral teeth of equal size to median teeth but it can easily be separated from the same in having entire surface of carapace weakly granular, 29-pectinal teeth are present and by the other characters as noted in the key and description.

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of scorpion venom

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of scorpion venom were performed under denaturing condition using SDS (Sodium dodecyl sulphate) and β -mercaptoethanol as denaturing agent MW-SDS 70L, standard curve. The markers include bovine serum (66.0 KDa), egg albumin (45.0 KDa), glyceraldehyde (3-phosphate, dehydrogenase (36.0 KDa), carbonic anhydrase (29.0 KDa), trypsinogen (24.0 KDa), trypsin inhibitor (20.1 KDa) and a-lactalbumin 14.2 (KDa). All venoms samples showed multiple bands in the molecular weight range of 70.0 to 14.0 KDa. *Vachonus* venoms also exhibited multiple bands of equal intensity.

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Gel filtration chromatography of *Vachonus*

1000 mg of *Vachonus asiyaee* and *V. iqbalii* venoms were applied separately on to the Sephadex G-50 column (2.5 x 90.0 cm) and eluted with 0.1 M, ammonium acetate buffer (PH 6.90). both venom samples resolved into six peaks (I to VI), exhibiting rather similar molecular mass range, *Vachonus asiyaee* resolved into one very major peak, three moderate and one minor peak, *Vachonus iqbalii* resolved into two major, three moderate and one minor peak.

DISCUSSION

The genus *Vachonus* Tikader and Bastawade described and recorded from Oriental region, Rajasthan to accommodating two species. This genus plays sister group relationship with *Comsobuthus* Vachon by their synapomorphies like lateral eyes small not bulging and lateral tubercles not elevated and outgroup relationship by its autapomorphies viz. posterior median carinae of carapace joining with the central median carinae but neither straight nor spiniform posteriorly and interior lateral carinae of 5th caudal segment unevenly granular.

Presently this genus includes four species including two new species from Pakistan. Among these *rajasthanicus* Vachon and *asiyaee* (sp.n.) plays sister group relationship to each other by their synapomorphies movable finger of pedipalpi provided with 10-11 very minute lateral granules pectinal teeth 22 in number in female and 28 in male and aculeus more than as long as vesicular length and outgrowth relationship with *atrostriatus* Pocock and *iqbalii* sp.n. by their synapomorphies moveable finger of pedipalpi provided with 12-lateral tooth, pectinal teeth 26 in number in female and 20 in male, and aculeus as long as vesicular length.

With reference to Gel filtration chromatography of *Vachonus*, the *V. iqbalii* shows more advanced than *V. asiyaee* in having two major, three moderate and one minor peaks (Fig 22).

Illustration of figures

Figs. 1-11 *Vachonus asiyaee* (sp.n.): 1. entire, dorsal view; 2. Same, ventral view; 3. Carapace, dorsal view; 4. Pedipalpi, lateral view, 4a. femur, 4b patella, 4c. finger; 5. Fore leg, lateral view; 6. Telson, lateral view; 7. Pectin, ventral view; 8. Genital operculum, ventral view; 9. Aedeagus, lateral view; 10. Electrophoresis; 11. Gel filtration chromatography.

Figs. 12-22 *Vachonus iqbalii* (sp.n.): 12. Entire, dorsal view; 13. Same, ventral view; 14. Carapace, dorsal view; 15. Pedipalpi, lateral view, 15a. femur, 15b. patella, 15c. finger; 16. Fore leg, lateral view; 17. Telson, lateral view; 18. Pectin, ventral view; 19. Genital operculum, ventral view; 20. Aedeagus,

lateral view; 21. Electrophoresis; 22. Gel filtration chromatography.

REFERENCES

- AMIR, R., ALAM, J.M. AND KHAN, M.A.J. (1994a). Comparative study of toxins with phospholipase A2 activity isolated from the venom of *Androctonus australis*. *Pakistan J. Zool.*, 26 (2): 127-133.
- AMIR, R. ALAM, J.M. AND KHAN, M.A.J. (1994b). Investigation scorpion venoms as naval insecticides. *J. Entomol. Karachi*, 9: 109-114.
- AMIR, R., ALAM, J.M. AND KHAN, M.A.J. (1994c). Procoagulant property of some medically important scorpion from Sindh region. *Pakistan J. Zool.*, 26 (3): 261-263.
- AMIR, R., ALAM, J.M. AND KHAN, M.A.J. (1994d). Comparative studies on the enzymatic content of venoms from fifteen scorpion species from Sindh region. *Pakistan J. Zool.*, 26 (1): 77-79.
- AMIR, R., ALAM, J.M. AND KHAN, M.A.J. (1995). Insecticidal activity of toxic components from scorpion venoms and their effects on cationic concentration Haemolymph of *Periplaneta americana*. *Pakistan j. Entomol. Karachi*, 10: 45-49.
- AMIR, R., KAMALUDDIN, S. AND KHAN, M.A.J. (2003). Redescription of *Androctonus* sp. (Scorpionida: Buthidae) from Sindh Pakistan with special reference to its genitalia and chemical analysis of venom. *J. nat. hist. wildl.* 2 (2): 21-25.
- AMIR, R., KAMALUDDIN, S. AND KHAN, M.A.J. (2004). Redescription of *Odontobuthus doriae odonturus* (Pocock), (Arachnida; Scorpionida; Buthidae) from Pakistan with special reference to its male genitalia, chromatography and electrophoresis of venom. *J. nat. hist. Wilde.* 3 (1): 17-21.
- AMIR, R. KAMALUDDIN, S. (2008). Revision of the genus *Isometrus* Hemprich and Ehrenberg (Scorpionida: Buthidae: Centruurinae) with description of two new species and cladistic relationship from Pakistan. *Pakistan j. entomol. Karachi.* 23 (1&2): 31-40.
- POCOCK, R. L. (1887). Description of some new species of scorpions from India. *J. Bombay nat. hist. soc.* 11: 102-117.
- POCOCK, R. L. (1900). Fauna of British India. *Faun. Brit. Ind. Arachn London:* 1-79.
- TIKADAR, B.K AND BASTAWADE, D.B. (1983). The fauna of India Scorpions (Scorpionida and Arachnida). *Zool. Sur. Ind;* 3: 1-671.
- VACHON, M. (1950). Apropos d'un nouvea Scorpion de Mauritanie: *Compsobuthus beslandisy*. *Nov. Bull. Mus. Natn. Hist. nat. Paris* 22 (2): 456-471.